

Phytochemical investigation of *Citrus reshni* (Tan.) flavido

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Abstract : *Citrus reshni* flavido has been shown to contain tricosane, β -sitosterol, 29-norcycloswietenol 3-O- β -D-glucoside, glucose and 5,7,3'-trihydroxy-4'-methoxy isoflavanone 7-O- β -D-glucopyranoside, the latter being a hitherto unreported compound.

Keywords : *Citrus reshni*, Rutaceae, 5,7,3'-trihydroxy-4'-methoxyisoflavanone 7-O- β -D-glucopyranoside, Kalidhar shifts, Kiliani hydrolysis.

Introduction

Citrus reshni (Tan.), family Rutaceae, is a handsome ornamental tree which bears fruit throughout the year. *Citrus* fruits are known to be deordant, aphrodisiac, appetizer, digestive, liver tonic, alexeteric and disinfectant. These plants are useful in vomiting, pectoral diseases, anorexia, dyspepsia and cardiac disorder¹. Since there was no report of phytochemical examination of its flavido (outer part of fruit peel), we undertook the work reported herein.

Structure of a new compound from *Citrus reshni*

Experimental

Flavido of *Citrus reshni* (10 kg) was collected from Department of Horticulture, Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, Haryana, India. The dried flavido was crushed and extracted with hot methanol. The extract was concentrated on water bath and the viscous material so obtained was allowed to dry at room temperature. The various compounds of the extract were separated using silica gel (60–120 mesh) column chromatography involving solvents of increasing polarity. Five compounds (A to E) were isolated and characterized.

The melting points were determined on Ganson apparatus; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) on Bruker AC-300F (300 MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard; IR spectra (nujol) on Hitachi 570 spectrophotometer; and Mass spectra on VG-70S 11-250 J GCMS-DS spectrometer.

Results and discussion

Elutions with (i) petroleum ether, (ii) benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 3), (iii) ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 3), (iv) methanol-ethyl acetate (1 : 49) and (v) methanol-ethyl acetate (1 : 19) afforded the five compounds. A comparison of spectral data and other properties with literature data settled compound A (10 mg, m.p. 50 °C, lit.² m.p. 47.4 °C); compound B (20 mg, m.p. 135 °C, lit.³ m.p. 136–137 °C); compound C (30 mg, m.p. 162 °C, lit.⁴ m.p. 165 °C); compound E (50 mg, m.p. 148 °C, lit.⁵ m.p. 146–150 °C) to be tricosane (1), β -sitosterol (2), 29-norcycloswietenol 3-O- β -D-glucopyranoside (3) and glucose (5) respectively.

Compound D crystallized out from ethanol, 21 mg, m.p. 230 °C (Found : C, 56.8; H, 4.92. C₂₂H₂₃O₁₁ requires : C, 57.1; H, 4.95%); IR ν_{\max} (nujol, cm⁻¹) : 743, 767, 815, 972, 1051, 1096, 1132, 1204, 1277, 1299, 1444, 1520, 1606, 1648 (CO), 2849, 2916, 3473 (OH); UV λ_{\max} (nm) : 336 (MeOH); 336 (MeOH + NaOAc); 312, 372 (MeOH + AlCl₃); 307, 368 (MeOH + AlCl₃ + HCl); 327 (MeOH + H₃BO₃); 358 (MeOH + MeONa); ¹H NMR of the acetate (δ , CDCl₃) : 7.16 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-2'), 6.95 (1H, dd, J 7.5, 2.5 Hz, H-6'), 6.71 (1H,

d, J 7.5 Hz, H-5'), 6.47 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-8), 6.31 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 5.50–4.10 (10H, m, 7 sugar protons, 3 isoflavanone protons), 3.90 (3H, s, OCH₃), 2.38 (3H, s, OAc), 2.33 (3H, s, OAc), 2.01 (3H, s, OAc), 2.03 (3H, s, OAc), 2.04 (3H, s, OAc), 2.05 (3H, s, OAc); MS (m/z): 466 (M⁺, 22), 463 (12), 430 (10), 419 (6), 381 (12), 352 (14), 315 (56), 202 (100). Molish Test : positive. Kiliani hydrolysis afforded glucose and the known compound⁶ 5,7,3'-trihydroxy-4'-methoxyisoflavanone (6), an yellow oil, UV λ_{\max} (nm) : 274, 307 (MeOH); 277, 328 (MeOH + NaOAc); 319, 372 (MeOH + AlCl₃); 319, 372 (MeOH + AlCl₃ + HCl).

The IR spectrum of compound D exhibited the presence of hydroxyl group (3473 cm⁻¹) and carbonyl group (1648 cm⁻¹). The GCMS and elemental analysis suggested the molecular formula to be C₂₂H₂₃O₁₁ and molecular mass to be 466. The ¹H NMR (δ , CDCl₃) of the acetate showed a doublet (J 2.5 Hz) at δ 7.16, for one proton, which could be due to H-2' of an isoflavanone having no substituent at C-6'. A double doublet (J 7.5, 2.5 Hz) at δ 6.95, for one proton, could be due to H-6'. Another doublet (J 7.5 Hz) at δ 6.71, for one proton, could be due to H-5'. Two doublets (J 2.5 Hz each) at δ 6.47 and 6.31, each for one proton, were assignable to H-8 and H-6 respectively. A multiplet in the range δ 5.50–4.10, for 10 protons, was assignable to seven protons of glucose and three protons of the C-ring of an isoflavanone. A singlet at δ 3.90, for three protons, was assignable to an aromatic methoxyl group. Two singlets at δ 2.38 (3H) and 2.33 (3H), could be due to two phenolic acetoxylys. Four singlets at δ 2.01, 2.03, 2.04 and 2.05 each for 3H, were assignable to four acetoxylys of glucose. The original compound did not show any change in UV when sodium acetate was added to it, indicating 7-hydroxyl to be substituted. When sodium acetate was added to the aglycone, there was a bathochromic shift indicating 7-hydroxy to be free in the aglycone. These observations suggested the presence of glucose at C-7 of the isoflavanone. On the basis of this data, compound D was characterized as 5,7,3'-

trihydroxy-4'-methoxy isoflavanone 7-O- β -D-glucopyranoside (4) which is a hitherto unreported compound.

Kalidhar shifts⁷ for 7-O-glycosylation (7-4), obtained from the peracetates of ferreirin⁸, i.e. 5,7,2'-trihydroxy-4'-methoxyisoflavanone (7) [δ 6.50, H-6; 66.70, H-8] and 5,7,3'-trihydroxy-4'-methoxyisoflavanone 7-O- β -D-glucopyranoside (4) [δ 6.31, H-6; δ 6.41, H-8] are Δ H-6 = 0.19 and Δ H-8 = 0.29, which lend support to the position of glucose in the proposed structure (4). As of 6 (aglycone of 4) and 7 have identical A-rings, Kalidhar shifts from 6-4 and 7-4 are expected to be similar⁹ for the A-ring protons.

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